

ORHAN PAMUK'UN POST-MODERN ANLAMLANDIRMA BÜTÜNÇESİ: ANLAMIN ÖTESİ

ORHAN PAMUK'S CORPUS OF POSTMODERN SENSE- MAKING: BEYOND MEANING

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Orhun Burak SÖZEN*
Seda KARAGÖL**

Öz

Anlam oluşum sürecinin incelenmesi kısa alıntıların karşılaştırmalı metin analizi yöntemiyle hem Türkçe kaynak hem de İngilizce hedef metinler üzerinden özellikle seçilmiş alt temalar/paralel metinler üzerinden açıklamasına dayalıdır. Bu bağlamda, hem özgün bir araştırma makalesi olması hem de alanda gösterge bilimsel çözümlemeyi kendine özgü bağlamında kullanması bakımından dikkat çekicidir. Sonuç olarak, anlamın oluşum sürecinin yolunun açılırken metnin herhangi bir mesaj vermek yerine kaliteli bir kurguyla anlamı oluşturmayı tamamen okura bıraktığı, Orhan Pamuk'un alternatif/söylemsel okumalardan hiçbirini öncelemediği, hiçbir söylemsel unsura taraf olmadığı ve post modern roman alanında Türkiye'de bir klasiğe imza attığı sonucuna varılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Anlam, Anlamlandırma, Post-Modern

Abstract

The purpose of this article is decodifying the sense-making available in in Orhan Pamuk's literary universe. As a result for the methodological inquiry, Orhan Pamuk's texts as well as language are so elusive, non-finite, and bottomless that it is impossible to fix any meaning. It is the privilege of the audience to extract meaning out of Orhan Pamuk's fiction. It is undoubtable that Orhan Pamuk does not take side any of discourse within his multi-discursive fiction. Those elements are available in his good quality post-modern fiction in addition to his creativity with keen promptness on detail.

Keywords: Meaning, Sense-Making, Post-Modern

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Background:

This section generally deals with Orhan Pamuk's literary universe in terms of post-modernism, in this context multilingualism, polysemy, the post-modern language approach where language turns from a tool into a purpose and a transformative social element, and beyond this framework, the relationship between language, literature, and translation in the context of power relations in the world, as well as the concepts and understanding of the post-modern novel. Pamuk has crossed the barriers of global power relations and, partly due to winning the 2006 Nobel Prize in Literature, has reached countless readers around the world through translation. Today, the Nobel Prizes in Literature are tending to diversify beyond the dominant cultures of French, American, and English languages, and can also be awarded to writers from semi-peripheral and peripheral cultures. For example, alongside the mainstream literary works of the West, writers from developing countries have also been seen receiving the Nobel Prize in Literature.

* Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Orhun Burak Sözen, Gaziantep Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi İngiliz Dili ve Edebiyatı Bölümü, Türkiye, , <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4507-556X>, obsozen@gmail.com

** Lisans Öğrencisi, Gaziantep Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi İngiliz Dili ve Edebiyatı Bölümü, Türkiye, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7129-1375>, sedakaragol589@gmail.com

Research Purpose:

In Turkey, topics such as identity, religion, the Republican Revolution, popular culture, and the characteristics of the social fabric are framed within a critique that takes varying tones using literary devices like irony, parody, and exaggeration. This framework is striking in terms of detail and intellectual level. In this sense, there is almost a play within a play in his works. His fictional universe, thanks to its rich imagination, skillfully connects Western tradition with Eastern mysticism.

Orhan Pamuk is mostly aligned with the Western literary tradition, but his works are also in intertextual dialogue with the Turkish literary tradition and his own other works. For example, the intertextual relationship between the analyzed 'New Life' and 'The Black Book' is clear. In 'The Black Book,' the ideological/discursive depth that starts with Istanbul on the level of a conspiracy theory spreads into the deep Anatolia along the axis of mysterious uncertainties. However, Istanbul is the backbone of central elements like identity, duality, and ideology-discourse in Orhan Pamuk's melancholic literary universe. Because the author Ist

Metot:

Roland Barthes' semiotics and translation theory have been taken as the basis for interpreting Orhan Pamuk's works. In his text analysis, Barthes places secondary meanings (connotations) and associations at the core of understanding, rather than the primary meaning. Using this semiotic method, quotes were interpreted on a conceptual level and in terms of the cultural mediation of concepts, and their discursive aspects could be examined. Attention was given to discursive duality and possible tertiary readings. Postmodernism, after all, can be interpreted as a tertiary level where dualities are surpassed. Postmodern analysis reveals that language has no fixed core and assumes that it produces meaning on its own. In this context, the analysis goes deep into language, uncovering the contradictions of its subtle structure and, at the same time, opening up new depths of meaning. In this way, language becomes an analyzable object that is examined with great detail. In this study, although Roland Barthes' semiotics is taken as the basis, a parallel postmodern meaning approach was also considered.

Findings:

The obtained data has been discussed in the context of modernism and the limits of meaning, looking at ambiguity, the search for meaning, polysemy, ambiguity and Turkish nationalism, and ambiguity and the search for God. This is how the findings were reached. Turkish nationalism has been addressed in its various aspects within ambiguity and polysemy. However, no particular perspective is shown as dominant. In fact, this layered structure is part of the polysemous perspective. Among the sub-themes, Turkish nationalism/Turkish Revolution is also included in the context of forming Turkish identity. Here, Orhan Pamuk opens the door to readings that can be critical, supportive, or a kind of post-modern/Third Way. A similar situation applies in the context of the search for God. While a reading oriented towards Islamic mysticism and Mevlevi tradition is possible in different dimensions, a psychodynamic/psychopathological reading that is not focused on in this article or only superficially mentioned is also possible.

Conclusion:

The obtained data has been discussed in the context of modernism and the limits of meaning, looking at ambiguity, the search for meaning, polysemy, ambiguity and Turkish nationalism, and ambiguity and the search for God. This is how the findings were reached. Turkish nationalism has been addressed in its various aspects within ambiguity and polysemy. However, no particular perspective is shown as dominant. In fact, this layered structure is part of the polysemous perspective. Among the sub-themes, Turkish nationalism/Turkish Revolution is also included in the context of forming Turkish identity. Here, Orhan Pamuk opens the door to readings that can be critical, supportive, or a kind of post-modern/Third Way. A similar situation applies in the context of the search for God. While a reading oriented towards Islamic mysticism and Mevlevi tradition is possible in different dimensions, a psychodynamic/psychopathological reading that is not focused on in this article or only superficially mentioned is also possible.

Only the reader can create understanding. Novels do not provide any textual message, and Orhan Pamuk

does not take sides or encourage any possible readings. This situation exemplifies the postmodern understanding of language, where language is seen as an arena of power relations in society, does not transparently reflect thought, but rather changes and shapes it. Moreover, Orhan Pamuk does not have any main idea. The point here is the absence of a primary message. In other words, he does not have a tendency to convey a message. This new style of literature points to a new fictional approach where the school comes above everything else. Likewise, there is no shaping author over the reader. In other words, the author is dead. The sole ruler of a literary work is the reader. Orhan Pamuk translations are the translators' re readings. In this context, Güneli Gün established an equivalence by using American cultural counterparts for the textures and concepts of Turkish culture.

1.INTRODUCTION

This article attempts to decipher the codes of Orhan Pamuk's sense-making. He was 54 years old when he was rewarded with Nobel Literature Prize as the only Turk to be granted to him in 2006. Ultimately post-modern and at odds with his country's Achilles heels, Orhan Pamuk devises his literary universe on an intertextual and cross-cultural baseline. The baseline is hence inquisitive and interrogative with a Western gaze. As the sampling for the universe in this article is a self-orientalist query, there may be some preliminary starts but there are no ends in which his sense of meaning could be fixed. Furthermore, fluidity of meaning hardly allows his audience to stop and grasp the hints of meaning, thereby elucidating the meaning behind them becomes challenging.

The scope of the article includes using all means to attain the goal of penetrating into the post-modern universe of Orhan Pamuk's fiction and his English translations. Henceforth, his corpus of sense-making is going to be decodified and if possible, all his literary acclaim is going to be subjectified by his works and vice versa.

The article has two scholarly fields, literary studies and translation studies. Furthermore, its ultimate aim is attaining a semiotic result, thereby, semiotics is both an aim and a means as a method. As the research paradigm, it has an interpretivist nature with a post-positivist standpoint. Document analysis and comparative textual analysis has been specifically used for methodological needs. Comparative textual analysis has been used as unique to this article with non-random choice of excerpts. Henceforth, the article is both interdisciplinary and multi-disciplinary original research.

Apart from the Introduction, this article consists of four sections: the Conceptual Framework and Theoretical Background with subtitles focusing on Orhan Pamuk, the Methodology; the Discussion and Findings with several subtitles related with the subthemes and the Results and Conclusion, which ends the article with final remarks.

2.CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1.The Relevant Conjecture in Europe and Türkiye

Orhan Pamuk has been a bestselling author in Turkey where popular culture has dominated the literary landscape for long decades. Despite his literary value, opposition against him overshadows his universe of literature, which sounds more political than literary (Belge, 2007, pp. 1-3). Furthermore, Orhan Pamuk's trial on a Turkish court coincided with the commence of accession talks between the European Union and Türkiye in 2005.

On the other hand, if we look beyond the local, Bourdieu theorizes that literary rewards transfer symbolic capital of literary works into economic capital. The Nobel literature price is no exception. Thereby, when a new literary canon has been introduced into the international literary arena, such Nobel prize winning authors and poets are translated largely into European languages. Though Nobel prize is autonomous, there is relative heteronomy of the relevant criteria in selection of literature laureates. Whether ideological or economic parameters have been involved has been controversial. However, the intersectional and Western domination which have underlined the selection criteria have had the tendency

to evolve into diversity and inclusiveness (Sapiro, 2023, p. 2).

Pascale Casanova argues that Nobel Prize has contributed to unify a world literature ground relatively moving autonomously from economic and political constraints such as nationalism, thereby constructing a global literary canon with widely translated winner literary texts. Such translational acts have involved publishers and literary agents in making symbolic reputation into economic returns. Access to international recognition is bound by both the intrinsic qualities such as originality or timeliness. And the extrinsic factors. Power relations between social groups or social conditions of the circulation of literary works, such as symbolic capital of the languages involved, that is whether they are central or peripheral languages are some extrinsic factors. A third group of factors consist of symbolic capital of the author as well as other features such as gender, race and nationality, the author's social capital. Furthermore, the genre novel has dominated the literary ground since the end of the nineteenth century unlike marginalized poetry and drama. Genre novel has been the gift of bourgeois class which has bourgeoned throughout the 20th and 21st centuries was the gift of Orhan Pamuk (Sapiro, 2023, pp.3-4).

At the deepest level the search is for the meaning or mystery of life his novel *the New Life*, the deep Anatolia opens into layers endlessly making to understand it almost impossible. Search, journey, circulation, secret meanings, maturity in the process as Sufi themes only form the structural or fictional framework of the novel just like in *the Black Book* and they do not drive a religious or spiritual essence for the novel (Cengiz, 2019, p.460).

2.2.Orhan Pamuk's Universe

Orhan Pamuk's fiction is closer to the European tradition than that of Yashar Kemal, a great storyteller from Anatolia who created an epic hero against feudalism in the vicinity of local Taurus Mountains in his novel *Memed, My Hawk*. Orhan Pamuk both follows realist epistolary stylistic forms of Europe in *My Name is Red* and *Silent House* and uses multiple viewpoints and in *the Black Book* and *the White Castle* he follows both modern and post-modern fiction traditions in the continent. Although *Red* and *Silent* exhibit modern and post-modern novel features, they are also traditionally realist texts. Henceforth, Pamuk has the ability to combine a plethora of European tradition characteristics with local oriental narrative techniques (Tasneem, 2019, p.7).

In general, accumulation of knowledge about Turkish interpretations of Orhan Pamuk's novels is half-formed based on misconceptions and misreadings and thereby very inadequate by both general public and interpreters. Furthermore, thoroughly acceptable readings of Orhan Pamuk are constrained by limitations of knowledge characterized by orientalist and nationalist façade of Turkey. As a summary, Orhan Pamuk's literary creativity, albeit constrained by miss or half understanding partly by of Turkish commentators of his novel, and Orhan Pamuk himself transgresses the novel tradition in Turkey. Furthermore, Euro-American readings of him have been constrained by cultural illegibility concerning Türkiye basing it into its oriental nationalist landscape of essentialized nature (Göknar, 2012, p. 305).

Orhan Pamuk emphasizes primarily the significance of the modern individual and the humanly choices made by him in all his novels. From this perspective, the maturation of the individual ethically, aesthetically and intellectual self-existence, his/her growth and his/her becoming autonomous all set up the essentials of Orhan Pamuk's novels. All his fiction delineates diverse cultural aspects of Turkish modernization experience while filtering critically the attitudes both positivist or dogmatic nature. Henceforth, Pamuk leaves a ground for religion and spirituality in his fiction against rigid secular tendencies, does not negate them, treats them one acceptable legitimate way of life, but at the same time he mentions their limitations and pathologies. Most of his characters want to go beyond the tensions between secular-religious, modern-traditional or Eastern-Western, and such figures follow a clearer

modern existence with all its sufferings and tensions. The endless spiritual search of his novel characters that he has described by a certain sympathy makes up an alternative post-modern imagination that he has developed for skipping the above-mentioned rigid dichotomies (Cengiz, 2019, pp.482-483).

Orhan Pamuk's texts are full of smaller stories and anecdotes sometimes compatible with the narrative's flow and sometimes with digressions. His novel becomes the canvas for such differences and nuances with a magnetic center with gravitational pulls for all such words and images like or unlike with the narrative flow's aura. Such labyrinthine structures feedback the epicenter of the novel with all their intricacies.

Thereupon, he interweaves a pattern of symmetry and balance with attentive care about details including a rich texture of symbols, images and motifs. He elaborates a wise juxtaposition of light and darkness, black and white, grayness and radiance, and red and green. All such opposite motifs have been enriched by symbols and images from both Oriental and Occidental references such as the Quran, Rumi, Tolstoy and Proust. These images such as dark and bottomless wells, shadows, stars, sun, books, snow, etc. interweave the textual fabric with in-depth symbolisms and textual allusions (Tasneem, 2019, p.7).

Orhan Pamuk mentions he has been inspired by Borges and Calvino, thereby he has thought that literary texts consist of some kind of systemic properties that make them have metaphysical qualities. Upon the influence of Borges and Calvino such texts were introduced to the West. At the deep structure of classical Islamic texts such as those there are Sufi allegories. These are parables consisting of countless and in-depth literary games. Furthermore, Orhan Pamuk says that nineteenth century Western Novel and especially those novelists Tolstoy, Dostoyevsky, Proust, Nabokov, Faulkner, Borges and Calvino have devised secular ways of analyzing such classical Islamic texts. Pamuk further underlines that the Sufi-tradition necessitated Sufi texts should very roomy. He continues that in *The Arabian Nights* for example, there are a lot of details, stories, oriental and Persian influences which make the texture of Arabian Night an ocean of stories. According to Horace Engdahl, Orhan Pamuk's *Black Book* moves from story to story across endless tales and parables as if they had no end and as if there were no origin and bottom (Pamuk, Transcript from an interview with Orhan Pamuk, 2006, pp. 3-5)

Orhan Pamuk emphasizes that he has been influenced by Western writers just like Faulkner, Woolf and Proust within the mainstream modernism. However, he keeps his distance from Turkish writers of the 1960's and 1970s who supported social realism (Gomez, 2021, p.62).

Whereas Orhan Pamuk stays in the same city, walking on the same street and inhabiting his house in İstanbul which has been identified by his fate, by what makes him Orhan Pamuk, in his semi-autobiographical fiction, his writing style could be described as pseudo-memoir and a *Kunstler-roman*. His fiction is full of parallel negatives which combine the subjectivity of Orhan Pamuk as an İstanbulit and the subjectivity of an artist (Gomez, 2021, pp.67-69).

On the other hand, *the Snow* develops a narrative of intersecting and diversifying communities with different cultural backgrounds with dichotomies along East versus West and Türkiye versus Europe. His approach is historicist when he critically interrogates the repercussions of Westernization in early Republican era with a nuanced scope and elaborate style going much beyond sided critiques. The plot takes place in Kars with a symbolic sign of peripheral and marginal but at the same time juxtaposed multiple Ottoman and modern Turkish identities on a larger scale of negotiation, and compromise .

2006 Nobel Literature Prize awarded Orhan Pamuk for his quest for the melancholic soul of İstanbul which both clashes and interlaces cultures (The Nobel Prize, 2006).

2.3.English Translations of Orhan Pamuk

As Damrosch, Venuti, Casanova and even Franco Moretti partially and with theoretical nuances have

put forward, any literary translation may better have contextual specificity and if possible, must have a sociological approach rather than a linguistic approach for translation. Thereby, close reading of source texts with a non-universalizing, non-reductive and non-essentializing approach must be preferable. All the above-mentioned contexts signifies that such great literary works must be re-interpreted with a foreignizing reading strategies. Henceforth, the processes through which a foreign text has been created circulated and finally received by another culture via translation evolves into an attempt against the domesticating techniques of publishers, critics, editors and translators. The translational attempt aims to review its uniqueness by a massive attention by the target audience. Thereby, the contextual originality of the source culture has been tried to be at maximum level of influence (Mattar, 2014, pp. 66-67).

3.METHODOLOGY

3.1.Data Gathering and Complying with the Relevant Ethical Rules

According to Barthes, there is a correlation between signifiers and signifies and furthermore the sign is full and it exactly stands for meaning. Plus, signs constitute a kind of semiological system structured as semiological chains. Henceforth, second order semiological systems show connotations or metalanguage.

The conception of meaning does not only refer to words and group of words within the context of lexicon and grammar but rather than that it refers to connotations that is secondary meaning. Thereby, these connotations could be associations or relations textually and contextually. Furthermore, our textual analysis will cover the text thoroughly and contextually. Henceforth, we are not going explain the text but re-interpret it going beyond its composition.

Overall, the destination of meaning is its starting point and its extension through other codes, signs and other texts that make intertextual relations possible. Heretofore, it could be concluded that language is non-finite and structured, that is, it is a kind of communicative and interactive system. Analyzing the text is reinterpreting it across cultural citations and cultural codes and also their non-finite configurations across and beyond the text.

This article employs a kind of Barthesian semiotic analysis in that Orhun Pamuk is going to be analyzed by way of his works having a structure of recurring teams which constitute a kind of signification system. Pamuk's signification system which comprises of a plethora of some systems. Each of them provides the audience with new paths that contribute to sensemaking by the audience. Orhan Pamuk's corpus of meaning is the combination of individual meaning in the mind of each reader.

Furthermore, signification of Orhan Pamuk has been viable through recurring teams available almost in each reader's mind. Sense-making through the recurring teams has been at individual level by each reader. The reason behind that is that Orhan Pamuk gives clues about the team only by connotations and subliminal messages. However, the messages have never been sent with clear straight forward the ideas. Henceforth, there is no main or secondary idea in any of his work. Thereby, the signification is open-ended, never fixed but eludes at any level. What remains is just a word of connotations. This article methodologically employs Barthesian semiotics to reveal this word of connotations. As total, Barthesian semiotics are going to be the primary method to attain a kind of meta synthesis in order to discover his postmodern literary universe. It is in fact beyond the reach of meaning even with semiotic means.

As for data gathering tool, textual analysis and document analysis have been used. No use of interviews, questionnaires, observations or anything that involves human beings has been practiced. Thereby, no data gathering method which necessitate the approval of an ethical committee has been used and henceforth the article does not have one.

The article will have been the work of two authors. First author's contribution is approximately 75 % with the initial idea, and design of the article, gathering, discussing and analyzing the data. However, the

second author played an important role in the editing process, writing the article, and choosing correct vocabulary. She shared her opinions about the arguments and counterarguments in the article, which sometimes turned the study meetings into a kind of Bakhtinian dialogic discussions. Both writers cooperated and collaborated willingly and eagerly.

3.2.Data Analysis

Data analysis will have been conducted by document analysis, and Barthesan semiotics. Hence, the data analysis makes this article original research article based on a kind of Barthesan semiotic analysis which foregrounds the analysis of narrative structuring.

According to Neuman (2022, pp.586-588), a text is a relatively neutral resource to research because it has been written without considering that it will be a material for an academic study. The purpose of content (textual) analysis is revealing and studying the messages, symbols and meanings of a text. A text is written, oral or visual material which functions as a means of communication. Texts include books, articles, pictures, dresses, lyrics, video-recordings and photographs.

Textual analysis is a frequent research method in the humanities especially in literary studies and cultural studies, which helps to inquire the text with its cultural, social and historical context by interpreting it. As a kind of qualitative analysis, it interrogates the underlying cultural and ideological presuppositions of a text. It involves both the language and symbols within the text that make sense out of the text. Thereby, a text is what we make meaning from, and what a writer writes is a work and a text is what the reader gets out of the work. Meaning has its own materiality between people, the world, values, signifier and signified (Arya, 2020, pp.173-175).

According to Barthes, there is a distinction between structural analysis and textual analysis in that in real sense structural analysis is especially used for oral narrative (mited), and textual analysis is used for only written narrative. Our purpose in textual analysis is conceiving the multiplicity, polysemy clearly, imagining it and experiencing it. Here what must be mentioned is very basic processing rules for the text rather than methodological principles. Thereby, textual units are clarified by interpretations or *connotations*. Connotations may be *associations* and they show the signified. They may also be based on *relations* that can associate the relevant issue somewhere distant within the text.

Analyzing the text does not intend to re-construct the structure, but intends to monitor its structuring. Moreover, monitoring or reading is more important than the rhetorical composition of the text. On the other hand, it is significant to get the *starting points* rather than *arrivals* (in fact, meaning is nothing more than starting). What constructs the text is not an inner structure which is close and measured, but what makes up is an *opening point* for other texts, other codes and other indicators, that is to say what makes a text is intertextual relations. Language, which we have started to know is at the same time both non-finite and structured. Texts should be monitored across itself, the matters are cultural quotations, and starting points of cultural codes.

3.3.Research Questions

The research questions are as follows:

- What are the boundaries of Orhan Pamuk's corpus of sense-making in his literary universe?
- In Orhan Pamuk's corpus of postmodern sense-making, there is no fixed stable durable meaning and the mention layers of meaning have seemingly no relevance with content. However, this is not the case. All elements are relevant and correspond to each other. In addition, this is complex and multilayered. Thereby, the question is how meaning can be associated with sense-making?

3.4.The Strengths and Weaknesses of The Work

Comparative textual analysis has been limited with two languages only *Turkish and English*. Western

languages such as French, and non-Western languages such as Japanese if once had been used, the textual comparisons would probably have been diverse.

Figure 1 and Figure 2 have been designed by the first author.

4.DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

4.1.The Limits of Meaning/Modernism and Polysemy

It would be a modernist conception to expect any scrutiny in meaning, thereby to fix meaning in post-modern fiction such as Orhan Pamuk's would be highly modernist. Like language itself, meaning is floating in Pamuk's ocean of literature, floating at the surface but anchored at the deep level. Furthermore, his corpus of meaning is encoded on an intertextual flux of interwoven liaisons. However, even if they sometimes overlap, none of them matches with each other.

Orhan Pamuk has been critiqued for he has had an orientalist or self-orientalist attitude. He has a Western standpoint; this is for sure. However, his indecisiveness and in a better way of saying his in-between stand between the West and the non-West, sacred and secular, modern and traditional, Westernization versus stagnancy, nostalgia and melancholy almost always closes the door for a such a scrutinous comment. He is in-between almost in every controversy where his fiction involves. He almost never takes sides and he has no precise exact textual messages on which such a grounding could be built on. Furthermore, his affinity to the European tradition of literature as it could be inferred from Tashneem cited in *Orhan Pamuk's Universe* in the Literature Review makes him almost unique in Turkish literature of the last decades, makes the *epithet self-orientalist* inexact and not much precise. His discursive/textual/literary/narrative preferences do not make him imitative but highly creative, profound and ambitious.

Orhan Pamuk does not prefer to take side between controversial cultural dichotomies. He stands in-between. For instance, he follows such Turkish authors like Ahmet Hamdi Tanpınar who has supported neither the Eastern nor the Western traditions in Turkish literature exactly Although he has a secular family and education background, he delves in to the sacred, Sufism, Turkish court literature and Islamic texts.

4.2.Multi-Discursivity and Search for Meaning

Orhan Pamuk all through his fiction designs a pattern of search for meaning and devises an arguably postmodern literary universe across which a postmodern frame has been built with a huge range of intertextual literary means and devices from part of which world literature has stemmed. His query for meaning is not based upon modern or Marxian dichotomies. Thereupon, his construct for envisaging meaning is neither one- nor two-folded. For example, Osman and Canan as the hero and heroine are not opposite for each other just like black and white but they are not based on a relationship between self and the other, either. Whereas, from his standpoint, Orhan Pamuk welcomes the death of dialectical dichotomy. At the surface level, a dichotomous scenery may seemingly appear, however, at the deep level dichotomies function as some literary means to perplex the texture of meaning. The ultimate aim for doing this is to build up a network of meaning which has no bottom or ends.

Thereby, the search for meaning is both enigmatic and perplexing in his fiction.

SENSE-MAKING IN ORHAN PAMUK'S UNIVERSE

Figure 1. Sense-making in Orhan PAMUK

MAKING MEANING OUT OF THE TRICHOTOMY OF ORHAN PAMUK'S UNIVERSE

Figure 2. Meaning Components in Orhan PAMUK

5.RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

He does not abstain from keen topics and details which turn into polemics around controversies his fiction involves in with a pro-Western attitude. This is a democratic choice. Condemnations against his thoughts and works have diverse influences and repercussion in Türkiye and abroad. Alluring readers in Türkiye and abroad with his literary mastery, he is a popular writer in spite of all intellectual clashes around/against him.

He subtly intervenes the pattern and façade of the plot, topics and subtopics, he builds such texts just like in the calculated ratios of an architect, however his texts are not bound by textual messages, instead there are unmatching or nonoverlapping controversial arguments and counterarguments none of which make up a main idea. Thereby, his fiction is not only ambivalent but more than that highly polysemic. The role of his audience, native or foreign, acting both lawyer, prosecutor and the judge.

Thereby, Orhan Pamuk texts have a great corpus of sense-making, however, the meaning is bound and constituted by audience's readings and re-readings.

His translations spread both his fiction and Turkish culture on a span of large global audiences. His great achievement to be the winner of Nobel Literature Prize has facilitated the spread of his literary universe and fiction across the globe by way of translation as the global book market digests such international literary prizes significant benchmarks for translating and publishing non-native fiction books.

Global power relations do not endow with the non-Western authors higher credit than Western authors. Henceforth, Orhan Pamuk's achievement including *the New Life* in the global book market is significant.

Orhan Pamuk has an intertextual post-modern corpus of sense-making. More than that, he paternalizes his search for meaning with overlapping but not matching but recurring themes, topics, heroes and heroines. He just searches for meaning, but he neither comes to an end for this even endless search nor he displays any preciseness or exactness for textual messages. He vividly sets up a post-modern game in all his fiction, however it is the task of his audience to play in the game, he even never becomes visible-he is never a player. His game is a kind of making sense, however in this bottomless and endless ocean, the meaning is beyond all eligibilities of accessing. The game is re-set in every new reading by different readers. Sometimes he invites the audience to play chess with him. However, there is no winner in the end of the game. Highly eligible reader may stalemate with Orhan Pamuk. And this is *all*.

REFERENCES

- Alver, A. (2013). Orhan Pamuk'un Kar Romanında Doğu ve Batı Kimlikleri arasında Etkileşime Analitik Bakış. *Turkish Studies*, 469-482.
- Arya, A. (2020). An Overview of Textual Analysis as a Research Method for Cultural Studies. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, 173-177.
- Barthes, R. (2023). *Göstergebilimsel Serüven* (4. Bası b.). (S. Özpalabıyıklar, Dü., M. Rifat, & S. Rifat, Çev.) İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları.
- Belge, M. (2007, March 25). *Orhan Pamuk and Modern Turkey*. Retrieved May 10, 2025, from Over redacted Donau: <http://donaustroom.au/>
- Cengiz, K. G. (2019). Fakirlerin Allah'ı, Zenginlerin Tanrısı: Orhan Pamuk Romanlarında Din ve Maneviyat Meselesi. *DTFC Dergisi*, 2(59), 940-988. doi:10.33171/dtfjournal.2019.39.2.11
- Gomez, L. (2021, May). "Under Western Eyes" Rereading the Landscape of Ruins in Orhan Pamuk's *Istanbul: Memories and the City*. *UNITAS* (94/1), 55-78. doi:10.31944/20219401.03
- Gökner, E. (2012, Summer). Secular Blasphemies: Orhan Pamuk and the Turkish Novel. *Novel: A Forum on Fiction* (452), 301-326. doi:10.215/0025132-4573985

- Mattar, K. (2014, Spring). Orhan Pamuk and the Limits of Translation: Foreignizing "The Black Book" for World Literature. *Translation and Literature*, 23(1), 42-67. doi:10.3366/tal.2014.0135
- Numann, L. (2022). *Toplumsal Araştırma Yöntemleri Nicel ve Nitel Yaklaşımlar*. Ankara: Siyasal Kitabevi.
- Pamuk, O. (1998). *The New Life*. New York: Vintage International.
- Pamuk, O. (2006, December 6). Transcript from an interview with Orhan Pamuk. (H. Eagdahl, Interviewer) Retrieved October 13, 2024, from <http://www.nobelprize.org>
- Pamuk, O. (2020). *Yeni Hayat* (11 b.). (M. Yalçın, & D. Halzebegoğlu, Dü) İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları.
- Pezzini, I. (2017). Semiotics as a critical discourse: Roland Barthes' MYthologies. 351-360. doi:10.1515/9781501503825-017
- Sapiro, G. (2023). The Symbolic Economy of the Nobel Prize in literature: how it contests or reproduces modes of domination. *Poetics* (101), 1-26. doi:doi.org/10.1016.poeric2023-101823
- Thasneem, U. O. (2019). *Orhan Pamuk and the Poetics of Fiction* (1 ed.). Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- The Nobel Prize. (2006). Retrieved August 9, 2025, from The Nobel Prize in Literature 2006: <http://nobelprize.org/>